

REVITALIZING MAHALLA IN SAMARKAND STUDENT DESIGN EXERCISE JOINT STUDIO PROGRAM SAMDAQU UII 2024

Dr. Revianto Budi Santosa, Universitas Islam Indonesia
Dr. Yulianto Purwono Prihatmaji, Universitas Islam Indonesia
Dr. Kamalova Dilnoza Zaynidinovna, SamSACU
Dr. Rahimov Laziz Abduazizovich, SamSACU

Abstract

Conserving living heritage should involve comprehensive approach integrating the management of historic built-environment and the living culture sustaining the existence of such heritage for centuries. Mahalla in Samarkand is a perfect example of living heritage of vernacular urban habitat, though now this type of settlement is under economic and modernization pressures. This Joint Studio Program attempts to involve students to understand the contemporary situations of mahalla around Gur I Amir and propose good design in some strategic sections to revitalise the mahalla by conserving the heritage while improving the living quality of people and enhance the attractiveness of the place for visitors. Employing placemaking and urban heritage conservation approach at micro level, this program train students to work in global collaborative atmosphere with mutual cultural understanding to introduce special design for each distinctive location.

Keywords: historic district, heritage conservation, placemaking, urban design.

Introduction

More than mere residential areas, Samarkand's mahallas embody the city's rich history and cultural diversity, serving as living examples of communal life that continue to thrive amidst modern pressures and developments. They are an integral yet distinctive part of the city's cultural and urban landscape. Architecturally, mahallas are characterized by courtyard house arranged in a organic structure, interconnected by narrow streets and alleys. Mahallas feature essential elements such as mosques, teahouses, and commercial spaces. These elements and arrangement fosters a strong sense of community among residents. Socially, mahallas still function in religious ceremonies, managing local resources and services, mediating disputes among residents, and are recognized as local governance units that facilitate access to public goods and social protection.

Mahallas around Gur I Amir have special circumstances as they are directly related to the major historic monument of the city attracting visitors from all over the world. To enhance the appearance of the monuments the government recently constructed tall walls around Gur I Amir. These perimeter walls ensure the visual quality of the domed monument without the obstruction of the organic neighborhood. However, it severe visual and physical connectivities between Gur I Amir existing for centuries.

The growth of tourism give economic benefits to some of the people in business related to tourist services, but it also give some disadvantages to the inhabitants in general. The distinctive characteristics of the mahalla need to be enhanced by proposing culturally sensitive design which are also improve the living quality of the people.

Five locations are selected to study and design in Gur I Amir mahalla with diverse conditions, characters and challenges. These locations have variety of relationships with communal living and tourism so that improving

these spots may affect the quality of life for the whole mahalla.

The efforts to improve the liveability and to enhance the attractiveness of the mahalla is carried out by combining placemaking and urban historic preservation approach. Placemaking is defined as the collaborative process of shaping public spaces aiming to improve a community's cultural, economic, social, and environmental conditions. To achieve those aims, placemaking initiative involves various stakeholders, including residents, local businesses, and government entities, working together to create vibrant and functional spaces that reflect the community's identity and history.

In enhancing the quality of life within a historic district with rich living culture, it is necessary to integrate between placemaking initiatives an historic preservation approaches. Historic preservation plays a crucial role in maintaining significant buildings and landscapes that provide a tangible connection to the past. These valuable elements evoke historical narratives and foster a sense of belonging among residents enhancing cultural continuity and collective memory, making public spaces more meaningful.

One strategy to deploy in this integrated efforts is by balancing modern needs with historical integrity. As communities evolve for centuries, there may be pressure to modernize spaces in ways that could undermine their historical significance. Effective placemaking strategies must find a middle ground that honors the past while accommodating future growth.

Moreover, many historict districts now is attractive to tourist with special interest to the dynamic culture. Places with historical significance not only attract visitors but also larger investments in tourism services. These larger scale commercial services to some extents may marginalize local people leading to gentrification or displacement of long-standing residents. Economic sustainability of the locals should be a core consideration in any placemaking initiative.

A Joint Studio Program involving students and teaching staffs from Department of Architecture Samarkand State Architecture and Construction University and Universitas Islam Indonesia is carried out to train students to study and design a distinctive historic neighborhood in Samarkand to develop their cultural sensitivity and ability to work in global collaboration.

Method

This Joint Studio Program aims to improve students' understanding of rich cultural significances of a historic district and their ability to respond the challenging situations in the district with strategic designs. The place to study and design are carefully selected to have variety of contexts and issues. With these diversities, students may learn from one another how to develop cultural sensitivity, to understand local issues and problems, and to respond with strategic designs.

The program started with some online lectures delivered by faculty members from both institutions prior to the departure of Indonesian students to Samarkand. For Indonesian students these introductory lectures are necessary to familiarize them with history of Samarkand, its distinctive historic architecture, and most importantly the characteristics of the mahalla that they were going to explore and improve. One lecture introduce some theories on urban design and placemaking to equip students with fundamental knowledges. Offline lecture sessions highlighting some issues were carried out when students of both countries first meet in SamDAQU.

On the following days, students are involved in direct observation to Smarakand mahalla next to Gur I Amir. After conducting general observation, students are divided into five groups each consisting of Indonesian and Uzbekistan students to focus to particular locations in the mahalla. The locations to revitalize are characterized as follows:

1) The Entrance Section: Around the entrance to the mahalla near the northeast corner of Gur I Amir complex and open spaces along perimeter wall. The primary issue for this place is the walls separating the mahalla with the historic monument. Visual as well as physical connectivity between these two districts can be redesigned in order to improve the sense of place in the mahalla as the integral part of the whole historic core of the city.

2) The OkSaray Section: Around the Oksaray Mauseloum with dense neighborhood and an open space with irregular shape leading to Gur I Amir complex. The issues to respon in the design the open space to be a livable place for the community and offer good visual connection between these two monuments to visitors, and to improve the quality of the boundary around the mausoleum to enhance the sense of place while maintaining the privacy of the neighborhood from the visitors' obstruction.

3) The Old Mahalla Center Section: Old mahalla center with a historic but dilapidated mosque, a tea house for the elderly, few structures no longer in use and

connected directly to the major access in the mahalla. This place has a good sense of place with limited activities to serve. To revitalise the place, it is necessary to to introduce some facilities to accommodate new activities with culturally sensitive design.

4) The New Mahalla Center Section: New mahalla centers is actually a relatively large open space with plenty of big trees, but limited use and little aesthetic quality. This green place is potential to serve as the community garden and park offering inclusive services to the people including children, youths and females. This environmentally friendly and socially inclusive could become a model for contemporary mahalla centers.

5) The Craft Center Section: Craft center near Rohobot Mausoleum is not directly related to the neighborhood but it is essential to improve since it affects the attractiveness of the whole greater Gur I Amir district. The government intend to develop this place into a craft center including facility for displaying and selling the crafts as well as demonstrating the making of the crafts. The strategy to enhance the livability and attractiveness of this place is implementing the government's program with creative design to celebrate the cultural richness of the place.

At the end of the program, students present their works in front of the jury in a crit session to review their works and enable them to learn from their peers. A publication is planned following the program so that the lessons can reach larger audience.

Locations to study and design

Result and discussion

After engaging in intensive discussions with lecturers and team members of both institutions, some preliminary design alternatives were proposed for each of the location, to respond to particular issues and challenges. These alternatives to propose are as follows:

1) The Entrance Section: In urban level, the tall wall serves as edge delimiting access and visual connection between districts. To revive the visual connectivity between these two areas the wall is changed into perforated wall with variety of articulations such as green wall and enriched with some traditional ornamentations. Some urban amenities like benches and light posts are introduced especially at the

junctions to give place identifications and improve services. Some guidelines for buildings facing the wall are formulated to give a more coherence appearance of this urban façades.

2) The OkSaray Section: The gate connecting this section with Gur I Mir complex which is currently blocked is revitalized by creating a small plaza in front of the gate to make this place is liveable and enjoyable. The boundary around Oksaray Tomb is redesigned to improve the aesthetic quality of the wall on both sides. The open space with irregular shape connecting Gur I Amir and Oksaray is developed into a flexible plaza with temporary structures.

3) The Old Mahalla Center Section: This place is the heart of the mahalla for centuries. Improvement with historic and cultural sensibility is important to maintain the strong sense of place already embodied in the place. The rear part with narrow triangular plaza is revitalized by re-using small rooms around this open space as library and other small-scale communal activities. To enhance the place identity and orientation, the surface of the street in front the mahalla center is paved with traditional pattern. Combined with pergola for grape vines above, this particular section of the street becomes very distinctive spot.

4) The New Mahalla Center Section: This place is characterized by big trees creating park-like and shadowy open space enjoyable for many outdoor activities of the inhabitants. Mahalla center traditionally is a male dominated place. In contemporary situations, this place may offer a more inclusive services for children, youths, and females who have very limited provision in the old center. Youths may have place for sports and performances in one end of the park, while children have playground at the central portions where most of the trees grow. Girls and ladies may have good place for gathering, reading, gardening with their fellows on the other end of the place.

5) The Craft Center Section: On the one hand, rows of shops with brick structures create coherence edge of the plaza in front of Rohobot Mausoleum, on the other hand these structure block the view to the plaza so that visitor walking to Gur I Mir do not realized this arts and craft market. A tall temporary structure is placed at the center of the court created as landmark seen from afar. This structure is treated as installation arts incorporating billowing colorful fabrics signifying the local textile making as well as the historic role of Samarkand as the jewel on the Silk Road. A temporary pavilion is constructed around this landmark to demonstrate craftmaking and to accommodate other craft workshop activities.

Conclusion

This Joint Studio is delivered intensively in very limited time. Nevertheless, it gives a number of advantages to the students participating in this program, among others:

- Developing cultural and historical sensibility and awareness of the importance of urban vernacular

heritage with living culture in relations with historic monument of the past;

- Balancing development and historic preservation in an urban historic settlement by enhancing the distinctive character and improving the livability of the place.

- Learning how to strategically observe the location, critically investigate problems, and creatively proposing design solutions in such short time; and

- Improving their ability to perform global collaborative works in real situations, overcoming cultural differences and language barrier.

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